

PATIENT AWARENESS AND PREFERENCES FOR PHYSIOTHERAPY TREATMENT OF ORTHOPEDIC CONDITIONS. A CROSS-SECTIONAL SURVEY OF PHYSIOTHERAPY AND PATIENT SATISFACTION WITH GIVEN TREATMENT

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Abstract

Research topic: Patient Awareness and Preferences for Physiotherapy Treatment of Musculoskeletal Conditions. A cross-sectional survey of Physiotherapy and Patient Satisfaction with Given Treatment. Background: With the increasing prevalence of orthopedic conditions due to lifestyle changes and aging populations, physiotherapy has emerged as an effective treatment modality. In cities like Rawalpindi and Islamabad, the availability of physiotherapy services is growing, yet there is limited research on patient satisfaction and the barriers that hinder the uptake of this treatment. Many patients often face financial and logistical constraints that prevent them from opting for physiotherapy despite its potential benefits. This study seeks to assess the current level of awareness about physiotherapy among orthopedic patients and evaluate their satisfaction with the treatment they receive, while also identifying factors that prevent them from seeking care. Aims and Objectives: Determine the extent of knowledge patients have about the role of physiotherapy in orthopedic conditions. Identify sources of information that patients rely on to learn about physiotherapy. Examine patients' attitudes towards physiotherapy and its perceived outcomes in their recovery process. Assess the level of satisfaction with physiotherapy services received. Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional survey was done using a convenient sampling technique. The sample size was 384 calculated through the open EPI tool. Data was collected from June to September from the study setting Bahria International Hospital, BBH, and other orthopedic clinics. The tools used in the study were SDM-9 and a self-generated questionnaire. Data Analysis IBM SPSS

27 sheet was used to analyze the data. Results People in the age group 18 to 38 were more aware of Physical Therapy, because of their high level of education and exposure to social factors. 26.3% people consider Physical Therapy intervention as very effective. However, people did not choose Physiotherapy due to barriers they faced. Conclusion: In conclusion, the study reveals that public awareness of physiotherapy is moderate, with many patients reporting satisfaction with their treatment. However, patient involvement in treatment decisions by doctors varies, with some patients feeling consulted. Although physiotherapy is often preferred over other interventions, the high cost remains a significant barrier to accessing care.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Definition

Physical therapy, as defined by the American Physical Therapy Association (APTA), is a therapeutic treatment using specific techniques to alter or enhance movements or balance, promoting physical and health conditions (Alexandria, 2001).

1.2 Importance of Physical Therapy

Exercise therapy aims to increase muscle and joint strength, improve overall muscle function, and expand range of motion. It relieves pain, reduces disability, and restores daily function. Therapists select exercise types, durations, and delivery methods based on clinical expertise, such as group-based programs, aerobic exercises like walking, or specific strengthening routines for core stability (Ferreira, 2018).

1.3 Assessment of Physical Therapy

The initial consultation involves assessment and screening to determine suitability for therapy. Red flags, such as serious underlying conditions, prompt referral to a physician (Heerkens YF, 2011). Without red flags, the therapist collects patient history, evaluates impairments, activity limitations, and contributing environmental or personal factors. Clinical reasoning guides diagnosis and treatment planning, often using tools like the numeric pain rating scale or Patient-Specific Functional Scale (Pietrobon R, 2002). Physical examination includes observation, movement analysis, and assessment of joint and muscle function. Treatment effectiveness is evaluated throughout therapy, using evidence-supported techniques like mobilization,

manipulation, exercise therapy, neurodynamics, and electrotherapy (Edwards I, 2004).

1.4 Techniques

Key methods include muscle energy techniques for stretching or strengthening muscles (García-Peñalver et al., 2020), joint mobilization such as Kaltenborn's graded approach and Mulligan's mobilization with movement (Mulligan BR, 2010), and myofascial release for fascial restrictions (James W. Atchison, 2021). Stretching—static, dynamic, or with initial tension—improves range of motion (Weppler CH, 2010).

Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF) enhances mobility, strength, and neuromuscular control (Sharman MJ, 2006). Manual lymphatic drainage (MLD) reduces swelling, especially in lymphedema (Cohen, 1998). Manual pressure release (MPR) targets trigger points (Simons et al., 1999). Neurodynamics mobilizes the nervous system to restore function and reduce pain (Coppieters MW, 2006).

1.5 Impact of Physical Therapy

PT improves movement, function, balance, and independence, reducing fall risk and managing chronic conditions like osteoarthritis, stroke, and spinal cord injuries. It can be as effective as opioids for some pain types, reducing the need for surgery or medication (Lindeboom R, 2011; Chou R, 2017).

1.6 Modalities for Musculoskeletal Conditions

Common modalities include:

- **TENS:** Electrical stimulation to relieve pain (Walsh D, 1997).
- **EMS/NMES/FES:** Stimulating muscles for contraction and rehabilitation (Gerovasli et al., 2009).
- **Therapeutic Ultrasound:** Enhances healing and reduces swelling (Kitchen SS, 1990).
- **Infrared Radiation:** Improves circulation and reduces muscle spasms (Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz, 2021).
- **Interferential Current (IFC):** Medium-frequency currents for chronic pain (Palmer S, 2002).
- **Thermotherapy:** Heat for circulation, relaxation, and tissue elasticity (Ishigami, 2001).
- **Cryotherapy:** Cooling to reduce pain, swelling, and muscle spasms (HOCUTT, 1982).
- **Shortwave/UV Diathermy:** Deep heating to aid healing (Rennie GA, 1996).

1.7 Effects and Uses

Exercise therapy reduces symptoms, improves function, and prevents decline (Taylor NF, 2007). Home-based and tele-supervised programs help overcome barriers (Hafez AR, 2014). PT benefits common orthopedic issues such as back and neck pain, shoulder injuries, and knee disorders (Di Fabio, 1998).

1.8 Musculoskeletal & Arthritic Conditions

Musculoskeletal disorders, affecting millions globally, include osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and osteoporosis (Woolf AD, 2000). They may result from age, lifestyle, or occupational strain. Management includes rest, functional rehabilitation, and modalities like heat, ultrasound, splints, and tailored exercise programs (Zvaifler NJ, 1974).

1.9 Repetitive, Spinal & Traumatic Conditions

Repetitive strain injuries like carpal tunnel syndrome, rotator cuff tears, and plantar fasciitis respond to stretching, strengthening, and supportive devices (Bisset, 2011). Spinal deformities such as kyphosis, scoliosis, and lordosis benefit from bracing and exercise (Negrini A, 2015). Traumatic injuries like ankle

sprains, muscle strains, fractures, and spondylolisthesis require tailored rehabilitation, often combining early mobilization, strengthening, and proprioceptive training (Kennet J, 2007).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Physiotherapy is increasingly recognized as a valuable treatment for functional motor disorders, supported by growing evidence, including randomized controlled trials. However, these studies often lack detailed descriptions of the specific components of physiotherapy. It is a common misconception that physiotherapy for functional motor disorders merely provides a "face-saving" solution for patients. Targeted physical therapy based on scientific principles and clear communication can effectively address the mechanisms that create and maintain functional movement disorders. To promote this approach, a geographically diverse and multidisciplinary group of health professionals collaborated to develop recommendations for physical therapy content for functional movement disorders. These recommendations are intended to assist practitioners and provide a basis for future treatment studies. (Nielsen J, 2013).

The purpose of Hills study was to develop a model describing patient satisfaction with outpatient physical therapy using needs theory and marketing research.

The model was developed based on interviews and focus groups with patients who had just completed physiotherapy for musculoskeletal conditions. It assesses overall satisfaction with physiotherapy treatment, focusing on the therapeutic encounter and clinical outcome. The model identifies factors that influence satisfaction and explains the relationship between expectations and satisfaction. The discussion includes theoretical satisfaction applications in physiotherapy, the impact of the model on the assessment of service provision, and its limitations. (Hills, 2007)

The patient-therapist relationship has long been recognized as a critical factor in therapeutic outcomes and is considered a key component of the therapeutic process.

This concept has been the focus of research in recent years and is often referred to as the therapeutic alliance, the helping alliance, or the working alliance. For the sake of clarity, this review will refer to it simply as the Alliance.(Bordin ES, 1979)

The spinal cord injury rehabilitation process involves several stages that last for weeks, months, or even years. Gradually increasing the difficulty of walking training in the community can produce long-lasting improvements in people with incomplete spinal cord injury. Exercise plays a vital role in increasing the activity level, life satisfaction, and overall health of people affected by spinal cord injury. The primary goal of physical therapy is to improve health-related quality of life by improving patients' ability to engage in daily activities. (Harvey L, 2008)

A review of the literature revealed strong evidence for the influence of physical factors (eg, activity level, treatment adherence and recent exercise), psychological factors (including self-efficacy, depression, anxiety/stress and feelings of helplessness), socio-demographic factors. (eg, social or family support and exercise barriers) and clinical factors in physiotherapy outpatient settings. New research suggests that health care system-related factors, particularly the patient-therapist relationship, may be the strongest predictor of exercise adherence in musculoskeletal (MSK) clinical practice.(Wright BJ, 2014).

The patient-physician relationship, influenced in part by the therapist, offers a valuable opportunity to improve exercise adherence in musculoskeletal (MSK) rehabilitation. Therapist-related elements such as tone of voice, positive reinforcement, empathy, guidance, clear communication, and trust play a key role in improving exercise adherence and treatment outcomes. These factors are modifiable barriers to

recovery and require targeted intervention.(Hall AM, 2015)

The meniscal tear is a common damage. About 222 of each 100,000 people can be treated with non-surgical or surgical methods. In the past ten years, studies have shown that surgery may not be more effective for patients with meniscal tears.

Based on this new evidence, the British Association for Surgery of the Knee (BASK) and the European Society for Sports Traumatology, Knee Surgery and Arthroscopy have developed treatment guidelines.(Thorlund JB, 2015)

Musculoskeletal disorders account for approximately 20% of primary care and emergency department visits. The healthcare professionals who most commonly treat these patients are chiropractors, family physicians, and physical therapists. Many related problems, such as spinal cord muscles and bones, accounting for 10 % to 37 % of the Family Physicians Bureau, approx. Family doctors or pediatricians can usually see children and adolescents who receive muscle-skeletal conditions, even if the spine or physiotherapist can treat them.(Whitman JM, 2005).

Physiotherapists play a key role in the management of osteoarthritis (OA), particularly in the development and implementation of exercise programs. Studies show that the positive effects of increased physical activity and improved quality of life can last for up to a year. Exercise is therefore thought to help reduce the burden of knee osteoarthritis and the associated costs for patients and health care in the long term. (Bennell, 2005).

Physiotherapist practice and person-centered care is dependent on a collaborative relationship between patient and therapist and is supported by the therapist's focus on the patient experience. Qualitative research is increasingly emphasizing the psychosocial impact of shoulder pain.

Although research on back pain has identified common problems across countries, such as employment issues, there is still a lack of similar comprehensive studies on shoulder pain.

(Miciak M, 2018).

Muscle pain is a common cause of physical therapy in primary care.

Constant pain is a complex, individual experience that can lead to disability and reduced health.

Physical therapy is designed to help individuals achieve a healthy level of activity and self-management by addressing physical limitations and understanding the condition.

This treatment is a collaborative process between the physiotherapist and the patient.

(Jordan KP, 2010)

Physiotherapists frequently treat patients with musculoskeletal pain, but the mechanisms that influence outcomes such as pain and disability are complex.

Research shows that therapist, patient, and environmental-related factors, as well as physical interventions, all influence clinical outcomes.

These contextual factors are often referred to as non-specific factors. (Indahl A, 2006)

Patients often find participation in mobility activities a major challenge during recovery from a critical incident. Overcoming barriers to early mobility is critical, and effective communication and trust between physiotherapists and patients are essential to align expectations and improve outcomes. Clinicians can use this understanding to better manage critically ill patients. Incorporating patient-reported outcomes to evaluate physical therapy interventions in the intensive care unit is feasible and may aid in their development. (Hojat M, 2011)

Overall, 201 respondents (51.1%) were satisfied with physiotherapy services.

Almost half of the respondents were satisfied. The main factors influencing patient satisfaction were age, marital status, prior knowledge of physiotherapy and general feelings about the service. (Endawoke M, 2021)

In Australian private musculoskeletal physiotherapy, personalized surveys related to education and shared decision-making were the strongest predictors of patient satisfaction and willingness to recommend services. Clinicians and educators should prioritize developing these

skills in order to create an effective therapeutic alliance and increase patient satisfaction. (Aharony L, 1993)

Starting physical therapy in the emergency department can reduce pain after discharge

However, patients who received physical therapy were more likely to use additional medical resources outside of the emergency department.

Nonetheless, those who perform physiotherapy in the ED are less likely to return to an emergency department during the year. (Weiss AJ, 2021)

Compared to patients directly entering the PT MSKD, the ordinary group of nurses was obtained from ED and upper issue for up to 3 months, PT clinical and resources were used for more than 3 months. (Gieski DF, 2008)

In our experience, physical therapist seeing MSK pain in the ED was associated with reduced imaging use and time spent in the ED.

Patients who saw a physical therapist were also less likely to receive an opioid prescription within the ED, a potentially important finding given the need for opioid reduction strategies. (James SL, 2017)

Patients in Northern Europe, North America, Britain, and Ireland usually report satisfaction with the physiotherapy of the musculoskeletal system in an outpatient setting. The main factors affecting patients' satisfaction are the skills of the therapist and the care process itself. Interestingly, treatment outcomes were rarely and inconsistently correlated with patient satisfaction.

Physical therapists can improve patient-centered care by focusing on and optimizing these key factors that increase satisfaction. (Law M, 1995)

The aim of the study was to investigate patients' understanding and perception of physiotherapy and to develop strategies to increase this understanding.

A cross-sectional hospital study involved personal interviews of physiotherapists using a pre-tested questionnaire over a period of six months (July to December 2007) with 200 patients in a physiotherapy outpatient clinic. The results showed that 90 out of 200 patients were aware

of physiotherapy, highlighting the differences in levels of awareness and perception among patients with orthopedic conditions.(Vaibhav, 2009)

The aim of this study was to assess the effectiveness of physiotherapy in patients with musculoskeletal disorders and their knowledge and perceptions about it.

An online cross-sectional survey with 26 questions (excluding demographics) was conducted using Google Forms.

Among the 260 patients from Delhi and NCR were 231 (126 men and 105 women between the ages of 20 and 92). Most patients have discovered that physiotherapy is effective, and reports of pain relief and attention, even if some people are confused.(Varun, 2021).

Shared decision-making has several advantages that transform the therapist-patient relationship into a collaborative “two-way traffic”.

In addition, shared decision-making can significantly improve patient satisfaction, treatment adherence, and overall health outcomes.(Sandman L, 2009).

Orthopedic surgery often leads to delays in patients with diseases of the musculoskeletal system. New models of care involving physiotherapists for diagnosis, triage, and conservative treatment are being introduced to improve access. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of physiotherapy-guided electronic medical record (EMR) screening using a locally developed tool to determine whether patients require orthopedic intervention or conservative treatment.(Brarua B, 2019).

For decades, patient-centered physical therapy has been promoted as a transition from the traditional medical model to a more holistic approach that addresses the biological, social, and psychological aspects of the patient's condition.

This approach emphasizes the importance of patients' opinions, needs, and wishes in their overall health and well-being.

As more people, including older adults with disabilities, benefits from physical therapy, there is a growing need for research to evaluate the effectiveness of this practice and quantify patient

experience and utilization of physical therapy services.(Jahan A, 2017)

Physiotherapists have become key providers in advanced or expanded practice roles, particularly in the treatment of musculoskeletal conditions. Many states have adopted these roles, which include tasks traditionally performed by medical professionals, such as making diagnoses, identifying candidates for surgery, ordering diagnostic tests, and prescribing or administering medications. These advanced practice models aim to improve access to care with equal or greater efficiency while managing costs and maintaining satisfaction among patients and healthcare providers.(Lebec MJ, 2009).

Several studies have shown that physiotherapists are highly competent in the assessment of musculoskeletal disorders, and both GPs and physiotherapists place a high degree of trust in physiotherapists as the first point of contact. Assessments in physical therapy clinics have also been shown to be cost-effective. Patients with soft tissue injuries in the emergency department can usually be controlled by a physiotherapist without a doctor.

When physiotherapists are the initial emergency contact points, this method is associated with reducing the waiting time for the patient and shorter accommodation.(Ludvigsson, 2012)

Physical therapists are skilled in handling acute back pain through exerciser and cognitive behavior strategies, focusing on the effectiveness of functional improvement. Previous comments have completed a combination of physiotherapy and multidisciplinary intervention measures without requiring individual assessments.

The purpose of this systematic review was to specifically evaluate the effectiveness of physiotherapy-led functional restoration for acute low back pain.(Richards, 2013)

Physiotherapy is a dynamic and globally recognized health subject, which plays a key role in managing various impairments and disability. It is effective in all age groups, from pediatric to geriatrics, and is used in a wide range of specialties, including neurology,

cardiology, obstetrician, gynecology, and especially orthopedics.

Physiotherapy techniques offer valuable treatment options for numerous conditions.(Greathouse, 1989).

Physiotherapy involves several labor-intensive tasks such as lifting, bending, twisting, range, performing manual therapy, and maintaining awkward positions for extended periods. As a result, physiotherapists and their assistants are at risk of musculoskeletal injuries. This study aimed to extend previous research by examining causes, prevalence and respond to work related musculoskeletal injuries among physiotherapists and physiotherapist assistants.(Holder, 1999).

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

STUDY DESIGN

Cross-sectional survey

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Convenient sampling

STUDY SETTINGS

Bahria International Hospital
Benazir Bhutto Hospital, Rawalpindi
Orthopedic Clinics

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size is calculated via the Open EPI tool. The total population of Rawalpindi and Islamabad is 2.098 million according to census 2017. Out of the total population 1.9 million people are aged above 18 according to our inclusion criteria. According to WHO the global age-standardized prevalence rate for MSK disorders was 17831.22 per 100000 population in 2019. In a population of 1.9 million, approximately 338,789 people would have MSK issues, which is about 17.831% of the total population.

Sample Size for Frequency in a Population

Population size(for finite population correction factor or fpc)(N): 338789
Hypothesized % frequency of outcome factor in the population (p): 50%+/-5
Confidence limits as % of 100(absolute +/- %)(d): 5%
Design effect (for cluster surveys-DEFF): 1

Sample Size(n) for Various Confidence Levels

ConfidenceLevel(%)	Sample Size
95%	384
80%	165
90%	271
97%	471
99%	663
99.9%	1080
99.99%	1508

Equation

Sample size $n = [DEFF * Np(1-p)] / [(d^2 / Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} * (N-1) + p*(1-p)]$

Results from OpenEpi, Version 3, open source calculator--SSPropor
Print from the browser with ctrl-P
or select text to copy and paste to other programs.

STUDY DURATION

Data is collected four months after synopsis from June to September.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Musculoskeletal conditions
- Age 18 above
- Decision-making capacity
- Able to understand and provide informed consent

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Cognitive impairments
- Conditions other than musculoskeletal conditions
- Co-morbidities

TOOLS

The tool used during the study is the Shared Decision Making Questionnaire (SDM-9). The tool demonstrated excellent internal consistency reliability (Cronbach’s alpha 0.925).

Known-groups validity was confirmed with Control Preferences Scale-post categories; mean SDM-Q-9 total scores were higher in the ‘Shared decision’ category (72.6) compared to both ‘Physician decided’ (55.1, $p = 0.0002$) and ‘Patient decided’ (57.2, $p = 0.0086$) categories. (De Las Cuevas, 2013)

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

Researchers should sign the consent form (present in the appendix) from participants before collecting any data, the researcher should let the subject give his data voluntarily without any force. Keep the confidentiality of the patient’s information. Do not harm the subject in any way, either psychologically, physically, or emotionally. Respect for the dignity of research participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

FREQUENCIES:

Prevalence of Age

Figure 4.1.1 shows that out of 384 participants age category 18-38 has a frequency of 166 and a percentage of 43.2, the age category 39-59 has a frequency of 141 and a percentage of 36.7, the age category 60-80 has a frequency of 77 and a percentage of 20.1

Table 4.1.2 Prevalence of Gender

		Gender			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Male	156	40.6	40.6	40.6
	Female	228	59.4	59.4	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.2 shows that out of 384 participants male have a frequency of 156 and a percentage of 40.6 while female have a frequency of 228 and a

percentage of 59.4%Prevalence of Level of Education

Figure 4.1.3 shows that out of 384 participants,71 people(18.5%) have education up till primary,100 people (26.0) have education up till

secondary,158 people(41.1%) have education up toll college/university and 55 people(14.3%) are post graduate

Table 4.1.4 Prevalence of Employment status

		Employment Status			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Employed	132	34.4	34.4	34.4
	Unemployed	132	34.4	34.4	68.8
	Retired	38	9.9	9.9	78.6
	Student	82	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.4 shows that out of 384 participants, 132 are employed(34.4%), 132 are unemployed(34.4%), 38 are retired(9.9%) and 82 are students(21.4%)

Table 4.1.5 Prevalence of Patient's Complaint

		Complaint of the Patient			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Post surgical	15	3.9	3.9	3.9
	Post traumatic	26	6.8	6.8	10.7
	Muscular spasm	113	29.4	29.4	40.1
	Repetitive strain injury	104	27.1	27.1	67.2
	Postural abnormalities	29	7.6	7.6	74.7
	Rheumatological conditions	97	25.3	25.3	100.0
Total		384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.5 shows that out of 384 participants, 15 participants (3.9%) are of post surgical , 26 participants (6.8%) are of post traumatic, 113 participants (29.4%) are of muscular spasm, 104 participants (27.1%) are of repetitive strain injury, 29 participants (7.6%) are of postural abnormalities and 97 participants (25.3%) are of rheumatological conditions

Table 4.1.6 Prevalence of Decision need to be made

Decision need to be made

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Somewhat Disagree	18	4.7	4.7	4.7
	Somewhat Agree	177	46.1	46.1	50.8
	Strongly Agree	151	39.3	39.3	90.1
	Completely Agree	38	9.9	9.9	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.6 shows that out of 384 participants, 4.7% with a frequency of 18 completely disagreed on decision need to be made, 46.1% with the frequency of 177 somewhat agreed, 39.3% with a frequency of 151 strongly agreed and 9.9% with a frequency of 38 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.7 Prevalence of Willingness in making self decision

Willingness in making self decision

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	2	.5	.5	.5
	Strongly Disagree	2	.5	.5	1.0
	Somewhat Disagree	24	6.3	6.3	7.3
	Somewhat Agree	183	47.7	47.7	54.9
	Strongly Agree	151	39.3	39.3	94.3
	Completely Agree	22	5.7	5.7	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.7 shows that out of 384 participants, 0.5% with a frequency of 2 completely disagreed on willingness in making self-decision, 0.5% with the frequency of 2 strongly disagreed, 6.3% with a frequency of 24 somewhat disagreed, 47.7% with a frequency of 183 somewhat agreed, 39.3% with a frequency of 151 strongly agreed and 5.7% with a frequency of 22 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.8 Prevalence of Different options for treating my medical condition

Differents options for treating my medical condition

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	2	.5	.5	.5
	Strongly Disagree	1	.3	.3	.8
	Somewhat Disagree	15	3.9	3.9	4.7
	Somewhat Agree	177	46.1	46.1	50.8
	Strongly Agree	147	38.3	38.3	89.1
	Completely Agree	42	10.9	10.9	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.8 shows that out of 384 participants,0.5% with a frequency of 2 completely disagreed on understanding of the treatment options,0.3% with the frequency of 1 strongly disagreed,3.9% with a frequency of 15 somewhat disagreed,46.1% with a frequency of 177 somewhat agreed,38.3% with a frequency of 147 strongly agreed and 10.9% with a frequency of 42 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.9 Prevalence of Advantages and Disadvantages of Treatment options

Advantages and Disadvantages of Treatment options

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Strongly Disagree	1	.3	.3	.5
	Somewhat Disagree	32	8.3	8.3	8.9
	Somewhat Agree	124	32.3	32.3	41.1
	Strongly Agree	165	43.0	43.0	84.1
	Completely Agree	61	15.9	15.9	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.9 shows that out of 384 participants,0.3% with a frequency of 1 completely disagreed on the advantages and disadvantages of the treatment,0.3% with the frequency of 1 strongly disagreed,8.3% with a frequency of 32 somewhat disagreed,32.3% with a frequency of 124 somewhat agreed,43.0% with a frequency of 165 strongly agreed and 15.9% with a frequency of 61 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.10 Prevalence of Understanding of the treatment options

Understanding of the treatment options

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	.8	.8	1.0
	Somewhat Disagree	13	3.4	3.4	4.4
	Somewhat Agree	138	35.9	35.9	40.4
	Strongly Agree	183	47.7	47.7	88.0
	Completely Agree	46	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total		384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.10 shows that out of 384 participants,0.3% with a frequency of 1 completely disagreed on understanding of the treatment options,0.8% with the frequency of 3 strongly disagreed,3.4% with a frequency of 13

somewhat disagreed,35.9% with a frequency of 138 somewhat agreed,47.7% with a frequency of 183 strongly agreed and 12.0% with a frequency of 46 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.11 Prevalence of My Preference in Selection of Treatment

My Preference in Selection of Treatment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	2	.5	.5	.5
	Strongly Disagree	3	.8	.8	1.3
	Somewhat Disagree	22	5.7	5.7	7.0
	Somewhat Agree	169	44.0	44.0	51.0
	Strongly Agree	166	43.2	43.2	94.3
	Completely Agree	22	5.7	5.7	100.0
Total		384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.11 shows that out of 384 participants,0.5% with a frequency of 2 completely disagreed on their preference in selection of treatment,0.8% with the frequency of 3 strongly disagreed,5.7% with a frequency of 22

somewhat disagreed,44.0% with a frequency of 169 somewhat agreed,43.2% with a frequency of 166 strongly agreed and 5.7% with a frequency of 22 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.12 Prevalence of Final Consideration of the treatment with my Doctor

Final Consideration of the treatment with my Doctor

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0	1.0	1.3
	Somewhat Disagree	27	7.0	7.0	8.3
	Somewhat Agree	165	43.0	43.0	51.3
	Strongly Agree	168	43.8	43.8	95.1
	Completely Agree	19	4.9	4.9	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.12 shows that out of 384 participants, 0.3% with a frequency of 1 completely disagreed on the agreement on final consideration of the treatments with the doctor, 1.0% with the frequency of 4 strongly disagreed, 7.0% with a frequency of 27 somewhat

disagreed, 43% with a frequency of 165 somewhat agreed, 43.8% with a frequency of 168 strongly agreed and 4.9% with a frequency of 19 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.13 Prevalence of Selection of a Treatment Option

Selection of a Treatment Option

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	2	.5	.5	.5
	Strongly Disagree	4	1.0	1.0	1.6
	Somewhat Disagree	22	5.7	5.7	7.3
	Somewhat Agree	174	45.3	45.3	52.6
	Strongly Agree	162	42.2	42.2	94.8
	Completely Agree	20	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.13 shows that out of 384 participants, .5% with a frequency of 2 completely disagreed on the selection of the treatment option, 1.0% with the frequency of 4 strongly disagreed, 5.7% with a

frequency of 22 somewhat disagreed, 45.3 % with a frequency of 174 somewhat agreed, 42.2% with a frequency of 162 strongly agreed and 5.2% with a frequency of 20 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.14 Prevalence of Agreement on How to Proceed

Agreement on How to Proceed

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Completely Disagree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Strongly Disagree	3	.8	.8	1.0
	Somewhat Disagree	12	3.1	3.1	4.2
	Somewhat Agree	153	39.8	39.8	44.0
	Strongly Agree	176	45.8	45.8	89.8
	Completely Agree	39	10.2	10.2	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.14 shows that out of 384 participants,3% with a frequency of 1 completely disagreed on the agreement on how to proceed,8% with the frequency of 3 strongly disagreed,3.1% with a frequency of 12 somewhat disagreed,39.8% with a frequency of 153

somewhat agreed,45.8% with a frequency of 176 strongly agreed and 10.2% with a frequency of 39 completely agreed.

Table 4.1.15 Prevalence of Choice of Decision

Choice of Decision

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Physiotherapy	205	53.4	53.4	53.4
	Other medical intervention	179	46.6	46.6	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.15 shows that out of 384 participants, frequency of 205 with a percentage of 53.4% decided to opt for Physiotherapy while 179

participants with a percentage of 46.6% decided to opt for other medical intervention.

Table 4.1.16 Prevalence of Level of Physiotherapy Awareness

Level of Physiotherapy Awareness

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not aware at all	13	3.4	3.4	3.4
	Slightly aware	70	18.2	18.2	21.6
	Moderately aware	123	32.0	32.0	53.6
	Very aware	151	39.3	39.3	93.0
	Extremely aware	27	7.0	7.0	100.0
Total		384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.16 shows that out of 384 participants, 13 people (3.4%) are not aware of physiotherapy at all, 70 people (18.2%) are slightly aware, 123 people (32.0%) are moderately aware, 151 people (39.3%) are very aware and 27 people (7.0%) are extremely aware.

Table 4.1.17 Prevalence of Learning Source About Physiotherapy

Learning Source About Physiotherapy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Doctor	146	38.0	38.0	38.0
	Internet	36	9.4	9.4	47.4
	Family/Friends	178	46.4	46.4	93.8
	Others	24	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.17 shows that out of 384 participants, 146 people (38.0%) heard from doctor about Physiotherapy, 36 people (9.4%) heard from internet, 178 people (46.4%) heard from family/friends while 24 people (6.3%) heard from other sources.

Table 4.1.18 Prevalence of Choice of Treatment

Choice of Treatment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Physiotherapy	245	63.8	63.8	63.8
	Other medical intervention	139	36.2	36.2	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.18 shows that out of 384 participants, frequency of 245 with a percentage of 63.8% considered Physiotherapy as a choice of treatment

while 139 participants with a percentage of 36.2% considered other medical intervention as a choice of treatment.

Table 4.1.19 Prevalence of Influential Components for Physiotherapy

Influential Components for Physiotherapy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Effectiveness	289	75.3	75.3	75.3
	Cost	22	5.7	5.7	81.0
	Recovery time	73	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.19 shows that out of 384 participants, 75.3% considered effectiveness as an influential component for physiotherapy with a frequency of 289, 5.7% considered cost as an influential component for physiotherapy with a frequency of 22, 19.0% considered recovery time as an influential component for physiotherapy with a frequency of 73

22, 19.0% considered recovery time as an influential component for physiotherapy with a frequency of 73

Table 4.1.20 Prevalence of Impact of Physiotherapy

Impact of Physiotherapy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not effective at all	16	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Slightly effective	29	7.6	7.6	11.7
	Moderately effective	134	34.9	34.9	46.6
	Very effective	161	41.9	41.9	88.5
	Extremely effective	44	11.5	11.5	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.20 shows that out of 384 participants, impact of Physiotherapy is not effective at all in 4.2% of the participants with a frequency of 16, slightly effective in 7.6% with a frequency of 29, moderately effective in 34.9% with a frequency of 134, very effective in 41.9 % with a frequency of

161, extremely effective in 11.5% with a frequency of 44

Table 4.1.21 Prevalence of Effectiveness of Physiotherapy Intervention

Effectiveness of Physiotherapy Intervention

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Moderately effective	55	14.3	14.3	14.3
	Very effective	101	26.3	26.3	40.6
	Extremely effective	49	12.8	12.8	53.4
	Did not go for Physical Therapy intervention	179	46.6	46.6	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.21 shows that out of 384 participants, physiotherapy intervention are moderately effective in 14.3% with a frequency of 55, very effective in 26.3 % with a frequency of

101, extremely effective in 12.8% with a frequency of 49 and 46.6% do not go for physiotherapy intervention with a frequency of 179

Table 4.1.22 Prevalence of Effectiveness of Medical intervention

Effectiveness of Medical intervention

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Slightly effective	32	8.3	8.3	8.3
	Moderately effective	69	18.0	18.0	26.3
	Very effective	63	16.4	16.4	42.7
	Extremely effective	24	6.3	6.3	49.0
	Did not go for other medical intervention	196	51.0	51.0	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.22 shows that out of 384 participants, medical intervention are slightly effective in 8.3% of the participants with a frequency of 32, moderately effective in 18.0% with a frequency of 69, very effective in 16.1 % with a frequency of

62, extremely effective in 6.3% with a frequency of 24 and 51.3% do not go for medical intervention with a frequency of 197

Table 4.1.23 Prevalence of Barriers in Physiotherapy

Barriers in Physiotherapy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Cost	173	45.1	45.1	45.1
	Availability	98	25.5	25.5	70.6
	Lack of information	113	29.4	29.4	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1.23 shows that out of 384 participants, 45.1% faced cost as a barrier in physiotherapy with a frequency of 173, 25.5% faced availability

as a barrier with a frequency of 98 and 29.4% faced lack of information as a barrier in physiotherapy with a frequency of 113

RESULTS

Table 4.1.1 shows that participants with age categories 18-38 have high frequency of 166(43.2%) than others. Table 4.1.2 shows females participated more than males having a frequency of 228 (59.4%). Table 4.1.3 shows that participants having education up to college/university have a high level of involvement with a frequency of 158 (41.1%). Table 4.1.4 shows that out of 384 participants, 132 are employed(34.4%). Table 4.1.5 shows that 113 participants (29.4%) are of muscular spasm. Table 4.1.7 shows that 183 participants (47.7%) somewhat agreed on their willingness to make a self-decision. Table 4.1.8 shows that 177 participants (46.1%) somewhat agreed on an understanding of the treatment options. Table 4.1.9 shows that 165 participants (43.0%) somewhat agreed on the advantages and disadvantages of the treatment.

Table 4.1.11 shows that 44.0% of people with a frequency of 169 somewhat agreed with their preference for the treatment. Table 4.1.15 shows that out of 384 participants, 205 participants with a percentage of 53.4% decided to opt for Physiotherapy. Table 4.1.16 shows that 151 people (39.3%) were very aware of Physiotherapy. Table 4.1.17 shows that 178 people (46.4) heard from family/friends about Physiotherapy. Table 4.1.19 shows that 75.3% considered effectiveness as an influential component for physiotherapy with a frequency of 289. Table 4.1.20 shows that the impact of Physiotherapy is very effective in 41.9 % with a frequency of 161. Table 4.1.21 shows that 179 participants (46.6%) did not go for physiotherapy intervention. Table 4.1.23 shows that out of 384 participants, 45.1% faced cost as a barrier in physiotherapy with a frequency of 173.

DISCUSSIONS:

The data revealed several key findings about demographics and attitudes toward physical therapy. Most participants were young adults (18-38 years old), suggesting that

younger adults may be more engaged in seeking health interventions. The participation of women was higher than that of men, which may indicate

women's greater health awareness or greater need for musculoskeletal care.

Education played a significant role, with 41.1% of participants having a high school or university education, indicating greater involvement. This is probably due to better awareness and understanding of healthcare services. The results were also influenced by the employment status, in which 34.4% of the participants were employed. Many people reported health problems such as muscle spasms, which are often treated with physical therapy.

Participants demonstrated moderate levels of autonomy in treatment decisions. Although many people have some understanding of their treatment options and the benefits of physical therapy, there are still a significant number of people who need more information to make a fully informed decision.

A large number of participants 53.4% recognized the effectiveness of physiotherapy and chose it as

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a treatment option. However, barriers such as cost prevented many from seeking physiotherapy, with 45.1% citing financial constraints.

Nevertheless, the effectiveness of physiotherapy was highly rated, 41.9% of the respondents agreed that it was very effective. These findings suggest that improving patient education and addressing financial barriers could lead to increased use of physical therapy.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, research shows that public awareness of physiotherapy is moderate and many people are satisfied with the treatment.

In addition, physicians involved patients to varying degrees when treatment decisions were made, and some patients agreed that their input was sought to some extent.

Although people prefer physiotherapy over other medical interventions, the high cost of treatment is a major factor preventing many from seeking treatment.

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